

THE EDUCATIONAL ROLE OF PODCASTS IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS*

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Abstract

This study is based on the premise that graduates of the 21st century must combine academic training with digital literacy. Communication and teamwork skills are formative and essential components of authentic learning. The purpose of this research is to identify the educational value of students' creation of educational podcasts. A descriptive research strategy was adopted to better understand the formative value of podcast creation by students. Throughout one academic semester, students were required to design, edit, and present an educational podcast while collaborating to complete the task. To evaluate the podcasts, formative aspects related to the following competencies were analyzed: documentation and use of sources, cognitive and socio-emotional skills, collaboration, and technical skills. The results indicate that the use of podcasts as a pedagogical tool has significant educational value in student learning; therefore, their integration into teaching, learning, and assessment activities is recommended.

Key words: *Students, Student-created podcast, Formative, Learning process.*

1. Introduction

Podcasts are media files that can be distributed via the Internet and played on computers and portable devices, including iPods or other digital audio players. Positioned at the intersection of digital and non-digital, the term podcast derives from the combination of iPod (portable on demand) and broadcast. It can be traced back to the 20th century when Adam Curry (a former MTV DJ) and Dave Winer (software developer) created a program that enabled users to automatically download radio shows from the Internet directly onto their iPods (this technological innovation played a significant role in the emergence of the modern podcast). Although the concept of "audio on demand" has existed since the 1990s, the year 2004 is considered the official beginning of podcasting; as a format, podcasts first appeared in the early 2000s (Berry, 2016). The term "podcasting" was first used by Ben Hammersley (2004) in an article published in The Guardian.

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Although podcasting initially referred to audio files played on Apple's portable iPod media player, video podcasts have since diversified. Currently experiencing rapid expansion, podcasting increasingly targets emerging markets, where education is regarded as the engine of economic growth. Kay (2012) analyzes podcasts from the perspective of both their benefits and challenges. Among the benefits there is increased control over learning, improved cognitive and affective processes, and enhanced academic performance. The challenges primarily concern technical issues and decreased class attendance. Despite these challenges, it is important to note that "affective and cognitive attitudes, learning behaviors, and performance are relatively consistent in supporting the use of video podcasts in higher education" (Kay, 2012, p. 827).

This study aims to identify the formative impact of podcasts as practice-based assignments and to promote their use in higher education. We argue that the integration of podcasts as pedagogical tools that employ new educational technologies contributes to the modernization of education and responds to the demands of modern schooling, in which students are active participants in their own learning, open to technological challenges and familiar with their specific features.

Among the messages communicated through podcasting there are educational ones. When podcasts are used in teaching by instructors, they offer certain advantages to students: independence from time and place, the possibility of repeated listening, control over playback speed, multitasking opportunities, and the ability to select the information that students want to access etc. When podcasts are created and presented by students, however, they require learners to communicate their understanding of a certain topic, coordinate tasks, determine essential information and supporting details, and manage their emotions etc. From an assessment perspective, podcasting evaluates what students actually produce and may positively influence knowledge understanding and retention. Consequently, podcasting can promote deep learning over the long term.

2. Literature review

2.1. Podcasts as Tools for Learning

Over the last decade, educational podcasts have attracted increasing interest and have diversified according to their purpose, number of collaborators, content specificity, and type of message conveyed. Learning through podcasts enables learners to understand the application of technology in the educational process and supports teachers in adapting to technology-based instruction. According to Moore (2024), "one of the common arguments in favor of podcasts is their ability to enhance student engagement and deepen learning" (p. 1139).

A distinction is made between "podcasts *for* learning" (created by teachers for students) and "podcasts *as* learning" (created by students for teachers and/ or other students) (Kendrick et al., 2024). Student-created podcasts foster the development of multiple competencies: digital skills, communication skills, interpersonal skills, and emotional competencies. All of these position students as proactive subjects placed within a peer-learning environment in which each learner acts as a

professional who learns through action, sharing abilities and experiences, interacting, and building relationships. According to Mooney, "in higher education, podcasting has evolved from a one-way platform for supporting academic lectures into an interactive, generative medium for experiential and engaged student learning and socio-constructivist co-creation" (2019, p. 3).

As Chan et al. (2006) observe, relatively few examples of podcasting in higher education are specifically intended to encourage students toward active learning (the examples based on learner-generated podcasts are even fewer). Lazzari (2009) makes a similar observation, arguing that most existing studies focus on user acceptance of innovation rather than examining its effects on student learning. In his research, students enrolled in a multimedia communication program were assigned three course tasks involving the development of their own podcasts. The study highlighted the formative aspects associated with podcast design, recording, and editing. These instructional tasks stimulated the development of reflective learning skills, encouraged students to explore issues in greater depth, and promoted collaboration among them.

Podcasts are usually delivered as pre-recorded conversations between two or more individuals collaborating in an innovative educational environment. Asoodar et al. (2014), who conducted both qualitative and quantitative research on the topic, concluded that podcasts are highly effective in motivating learners, are useful and enjoyable, and encourage active engagement in completing academic tasks.

McGarr (2009) identifies three pedagogical modes of integrating podcasts into educational activities: (1) substitutional: podcasts replace traditional teaching materials such as recorded lectures and audio presentations; (2) supplementary: podcasts complement existing materials (guides or additional resources); (3) creative/ generative: podcasts are created by students as part of the learning process (audio presentations and projects). Regarding the third mode, it has been argued that by producing podcasts themselves, "students can become creators of knowledge rather than mere recipients of knowledge" (McGarr, 2009, p. 317). Co-created podcasts, analyzed by Serrini et al. (2025), are also considered valuable. Both collaborative podcast production and podcast listening can contribute to strengthening the sense of belonging to a group or community.

There are several types of podcasts classified according to different criteria. Educational podcasts may be categorized according to their authorship (podcasts created by teachers, podcasts created by students, and podcasts produced by third parties outside the course context). Depending on their function, podcasts may be administrative (introducing rules or distributing general information), event-related, or integrated into the teaching-learning-assessment process (project-based podcasts may serve as practice-oriented assignments developed over a longer period of time).

As part of emerging technologies, podcasts remain an appropriate form of flexible and engaging learning experience for all age groups. Bajrami et al. (2026) argue that "AI-generated podcasts can automatically adapt content to students' levels of understanding and provide individualized and differentiated instruction for different age groups" (p. 143). Wakefield et al. (2023) emphasize the role of

authentic learning as an active process and highlight students' role as knowledge constructors, particularly in STEM disciplines (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics).

2.2. The Educational Value of Student-Created Podcasts

Podcasting involves metacognitive regulation related to the strategies learners employ during the learning process. From this perspective, metacognitive knowledge is essential. It refers to what students understand and believe about a topic or task and includes all the judgments they make when allocating cognitive resources on the basis of such knowledge. For cognitive presence to emerge, students require opportunities for active engagement in podcast production. It has been argued that "students strongly associate the role of podcasting in facilitating learning with an increased likelihood of passing the course" (Hernandez-Lopez & Mendoza-Jimenez, 2025, p. 16). Creating and presenting podcasts represents a formative process grounded in constructivist theories of learning, in which the teacher acts as a facilitator while students become active agents of their own development. Podcasting contributes not only to the development of cognitive skills but also to increased motivation, self-esteem, and emotional awareness (Wakefield et al., 2023).

Student podcast creation influences multiple dimensions of personality development: (1) it contributes to the formation of strong character traits (podcast production requires responsibility, punctuality, commitment to task completion, and meaning-making); (2) it supports the development of pedagogical aptitude (placing students in situations where they must design, organize, and communicate educational content, results into developing instructional design skills, pedagogical communication competencies, and the ability to integrate technology into teaching); and (3) it develops socio-emotional competencies, (podcasts become experiential learning environments in which social and emotional skills are practiced).

Socio-emotional competencies play a particularly significant role, being regarded as important resources in preparing students as future teachers. In an action-research study, Kendrick et al. (2024) refer to the research conducted by Forbes and Khoo in 2015, in which podcast creation was assigned as coursework: "they found that through podcast production, instructors and students co-created knowledge, while students and instructors acquired important digital pedagogical skills. Furthermore, they suggested that practicing and modeling the use of various technologies increased students' confidence in applying these technologies in their future teaching practice" (Forbes & Khoo, 2015, apud Kendrick et al., 2024, p. 883). Podcast production also contributes to the development of social skills and community identity (Barquero Cabrero et al., 2022). In addition, learning through podcasts has been shown to increase learner motivation (Carle et al., 2009; Fernandez et al., 2009).

Analyzing podcast use in higher education, Fernandez et al. (2015) include podcast creation by students among the relevant educational practices. Student involvement in podcast production effectively improves learning experiences (Moore, 2024), as well as technical and teamwork skills (Lazzari, 2009). Another advantage concerns the increased opportunities for demonstrating and developing a variety of

skills that may remain unexpressed in predominantly text-based assignments (Gunderson & Cumming, 2023). Collectively, these studies emphasize the fact that podcasts represent valuable perspectives for authentic learning and assessment.

Research has shown that students generally hold positive attitudes toward podcast creation (Phillips, 2017). According to a recent study, compared with video-based and gamified learning platforms (which often report stronger immediate engagement effects), "podcasts produce more consistent gains in listening comprehension, reflective learning, and self-regulated learning" (Bajrami et al., 2026, p. 163). Podcasts may be used to promote both foundational knowledge and advanced skills (for example, transfer, creativity). Students become content creators and capitalize on interdisciplinary approaches that contribute to meaningful and sustainable learning.

Rogers and Herbert (2019) distinguish between "recorded and broadcast" podcasts (monologic formats without interaction) and "interview- and narrative-based" podcasts (storytelling-oriented formats involving multiple voices and alternating perspectives). Both forms can deepen learning, but only when their value is clearly communicated and their purpose explicitly explained to students.

Podcasts have also been analyzed from other perspectives, including branding and public engagement with science. Beyond their educational use, podcasts may become modern communication tools and strategic vectors of institutional identity and reputation. According to Leandro et al. (2025), podcasts are perceived by university students as effective branding tools because they increase awareness, foster a sense of belonging, and have motivational impact. The podcast format allows the transmission of authentic narratives that contribute to institutional branding. Institutional branding, in turn, increases visibility, strengthens credibility, and differentiates institutions within competitive environments in which the "voice" of students and graduates can be heard. Cook (2023) presents academic podcasting as an emerging, creative, and accessible practice that has developed as an alternative to traditional models of scientific knowledge production and dissemination. He highlights the rapid growth of scientific podcasts as well as the diversity of existing formats (some based on interviews and discussions, others focused on narrative or documentary-style storytelling, while others consist of recorded lectures or events).

In the present study, we focus specifically on student-created podcasts. Such podcasts may take the form of practice-based assignments and - from this perspective - podcasts provide valuable insights into active and collaborative learning. Closely linked to the flipped classroom model, podcasting is considered a result of integrating mobile technologies into the learning process (Marco-Detchart et al., 2023). Analyzing student-generated podcasts as tools for engagement, Moore (2024) reviews the relevant literature and notes that many studies report student enthusiasm and active involvement in participatory knowledge creation. Students established connections between classroom learning and real-world issues through the creation, search, and synthesis of original content. He further argues that podcast use has the merit of "humanizing" learning experiences and contributing to more inclusive learning environments.

3. Methodology

3.1. Aim and Objectives

The aim of this research is to identify the formative value of educational podcasts created by students. This objective is connected to the following research question: *What formative aspects are developed through student podcast production?* The research question establishes both the area of interest and the limits of the study.

The objectives of the research are:

- To identify the characteristics of podcasts and the research findings related to their educational use, as reflected in the specialized literature;
- To evaluate the podcasts created and presented by students as part of the overall assessment process (the podcast represented the practice-based assignment prepared by Master's students throughout the first semester of the 2025-2026 academic year);
- To analyze the formative aspects associated with podcast production in the preparation of students as future teachers;
- To present the educationally formative elements resulting from the creation and presentation of student podcasts;
- To formulate conclusions and recommendations regarding the formative value of podcasts in the initial training of future teachers.

3.2. Organizational Framework

The research, conducted over a four-month period (01.10.2025-31.01.2026), was descriptive in nature and took place at the University of Craiova. At the beginning of the instructional program, students were informed about the purpose of the practice-based assignment, the evaluation criteria, and the time available for preparing and producing the podcast.

The sample consisted of second-year Master's students from the University of Craiova enrolled in the Psycho-Pedagogical Training Module. Of the total 122 participants, 82 students (67.21%) completed the practice-based assignment involving podcast production. The distribution across faculties was as follows: 36 students belonged to the Faculty of Sciences (Departments of Chemistry, Physics, Geography, Computer Science, and Mathematics), 30 students were enrolled in technical fields (Faculty of Automation, Computers and Electronics, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, and Faculty of Mechanics), 6 students attended the Faculty of Agronomy, and 10 attended the Faculty of Horticulture. The total number of students ($n = 82$) formed 41 groups (pair work).

The content sample included topics specific to the course "Sociology of Education", a subject included in the Master's curriculum.

3.3. Research Procedure

In evaluating the results obtained by the students, the following criteria were considered:

- a) Topic: appropriate selection (of the subject from the proposed topics specific to the course "Sociology of Education");

- b) Time management: compliance with the required time limit and respect for the imposed duration (10 minutes);
- c) Format of the assignment: co-hosted podcast format (two presenters);
- d) Mode of completion: collaboration with a classmate (work in pairs consisting of two members);
- e) Content: consistency with the selected topic, accuracy of information, use of sources (authors, books, articles), use of specialized terminology, and interdisciplinary approaches;
- f) Paraverbal communication elements: rhythm, tone, emphasis, pauses, and diction;
- g) Additional aspects: announcement of the topic, introduction of the interlocutors, background music, and coherent structure (introduction, main body, and conclusion);
- h) Platform: Google Classroom (MP3 audio file).

The selection of the topic (theme) aimed to assess students' level of understanding of the issues studied during the course. The use of Google Classroom represented a technical aspect and constituted a necessary condition for the presentation of the practice-based assignment, ensuring compliance with an essential requirement. Adherence to the presentation time limit reflected organization, discipline, and time-management skills. Compliance with both the format of the assignment and the method of completion represented technical requirements, but also reflected students' ability to understand instructions, as well as their attention, responsibility, and emotional self-regulation. With regard to emotional self-regulation, we examined the extent to which students were able to complete a complex task involving strict rules, time pressure, and clearly defined expectations. Some students initially stated that they were unable to initiate or develop cooperative relationships with another colleague in order to complete the task because of difficulties in emotion management or limitations in social interaction skills. Communication shapes the way students learn to express themselves, build relationships, and regulate themselves during interactions. The evaluation of paraverbal communication elements highlighted metacognitive competencies (How does the message sound?, What is communicated beyond words?, What does the message reveal about self-confidence?)

All these aspects capitalize on the formative dimension of the practice-based assignment by combining communication, technology, and collaboration, stimulating psychological processes, and developing metacognitive competencies. The study examined the extent to which the preparation, production, and presentation of podcasts by students involve formative dimensions within the instructional-educational process. The formative dimension is reflected in several areas: critical thinking in information analysis (e.g., source verification, selection of relevant information, argument construction, and synthesis skills), learning management (e.g., meeting deadlines, task distribution, and coordination among participants), development of technical competencies (e.g., equipment management, audio recording, and editing), collaboration and teamwork (e.g., role assumption,

negotiation of ideas, and maintaining a common working rhythm), development of communication skills (e.g., logical sequencing of ideas presented by each student, avoidance of misinformation, respect for sources, and use of paraverbal communication elements), as well as emotional self-regulation and self-confidence (e.g., assuming public exposure and managing emotions).

By participating in the various aspects of podcast production, the students gained practical experience. In addition, each group received feedback from the teacher, focusing on the positive and negative aspects as well as on those that need improvement. The observations, suggestions and recommendations were uploaded on Google Classroom targeting the contribution each group of students had.

4. Results

With reference to the first evaluation criterion, our interest focused on the extent to which students correctly identified and selected the topic of the practice-based assignment. The basic requirement was that the topic should belong to the thematic content of the course "Sociology of Education"; however, students were given the freedom to reformulate, nuance, or choose a more suggestive title. Among the most interesting titles proposed by students were the following: "Education: Mirror or Engine of Society?", "The School of the Future – Between Utopia and Necessity", "Education Through a Sociological Lens", "Man as a Social Animal", and "Education and Diversity: Challenges and Opportunities".

The podcast titles the students selected fall 100% within the specific topic. It includes the following large themes:

- Specifics of the sociology of education (history, authors, functions, types of analysis);
- Sociological theories of education (e.g. Functionalism, Symbolic Interactionism, Sociological Phenomenology, Dramaturgical Model, Interpretive Models, Structuralist Constructivism, Sociolinguistic Theory);
- Institutions and organizations (status, roles, types, perspectives);
- Organizational culture;
- Prosocial and antisocial behaviors;
- Equal opportunities in education (inclusive school, children with special educational needs).

A classification of the topics selected by students from the course themes indicates a particular interest in the following areas: social inequalities (13 groups: 31.71 %), the relationship between school and society (10 groups: 24.39 %), and vulnerable groups (9 groups: 21.95 %). The remaining groups also addressed topics related to the specific course content; however, the frequency of these choices did not exceed a significant percentage. Examples include "Man as a Social Animal" - 3 groups, "The School as an Organization" - 2 groups, "Organizational Culture" - 2 groups, "Durkheim: Education as a Social Fact" - 1 group, and "The Relationship Between Institutions and Organizations" - 1 group.

Figure 1. Selected topics for the podcast

Regarding time constraints, there were situations where either the deadline was exceeded or students used a smaller portion of the allotted time. Of the 41 groups, 9 groups (21.95 %) did not use the 10 minutes, 4 groups (9.76 %) exceeded the deadline, and 28 groups (68.29 %) met the required time.

Figure 2. Reporting on the time required for the podcast presentation

With regard to the format of the assignment, the required structure was respected by all groups. Concerning the mode of completion, there were three situations in which one of the participants did not belong to the student group (he/she was an external collaborator, such as a friend or a family member).

The analysis of the content-related criterion highlighted the following aspects:

- Agreement between the presented information and the selected topic: 92.68 %
- Correctness of the information presented: 85.37 %;
- Call to sources (authors, articles, research): 46.34 %;
- Use of specialized terms: 39.02 %;
- Interdisciplinary approaches: 26.83 %.

Figure 3. Podcast Content Analysis

The item referring to paraverbal communication tracks elements related to diction, pauses, emphasis, pitch, and rhythm. The analysis of these elements provides information about the communication competence of master's students (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Analysis of paraverbal communication

Other aspects that contributed to the creation and presentation of the podcast were also taken into account: announcing the topic (17 groups: 41.46 %), introducing speakers (18: 43.90 %), the presence of a musical background (8 groups: 19.51 %), coherent structure (33 groups: 80.49 %).

5. Discussions

This systematic analysis demonstrated that educational interventions in the form of podcasts have a significant impact on the formative dimension of student learning, particularly with regard to the development of thinking skills, cooperative social relationships, communication abilities, and emotional management.

Students were given a certain degree of creative freedom and were encouraged to think critically about the most effective way to communicate their topic, thereby promoting a culture of trust-based relationships with teachers. The topics selected

for the podcasts were appropriate (consistent with the proposed thematic content) (100 %), which demonstrates students' understanding of the specific characteristics of the course. Most students (68.29 %) complied with the required time limit. Minor exceptions were recorded among students who used less time than allocated for the presentation (9.76 %), while some groups slightly exceeded the imposed limit (21.95 %). These findings suggest that students were attentive to the time factor, which had an impact on their planning and organizational skills.

Compliance with the assignment format and mode of completion highlights students' responsible attitude toward the task. Even in the few situations in which the partner was not part of the larger student group (3 groups, representing 7.31 %), the students' willingness to complete the assignment can still be appreciated (the students identified alternative solutions that enabled them to overcome their inability to solve the task otherwise). Teamwork has a strong formative role, contributing to the development of critical thinking, responsibility, communication skills, as well as social and emotional competencies.

With regard to the consistency between the information presented and the selected topic, as well as the accuracy of the information provided, the findings indicate that logical and content-related connections were respected to a very high extent. This aspect highlights both cognitive elements (e.g., logical thinking) and regulatory elements (e.g., attention). The use of sources (authors, articles, and research studies) was observed in approximately 50 % of the podcasts, indicating a moderate interest in integrating specialized literature. Although the presentation of the content was generally systematic and well organized, more than half of the students emphasized their own interpretations of the selected topic, frequently supporting their ideas with examples drawn from everyday life. We believe that students should be encouraged, on the one hand, to relate educational content to their previous experiences and, on the other hand, to engage more thoroughly with the contributions of established authors who represent important reference points within particular fields of knowledge. Documentation plays an essential formative role because it develops logical thinking (e.g., students identify biases and distinguish between valid and unsupported information), improves argumentative skills (e.g., students discover theories, classifications, and examples), and fosters learning autonomy (e.g., students learn through discovery and develop their own learning styles). The aspects that still require improvement concern the use of specialized terminology and interdisciplinary approaches.

Diction is manifested through articulation (the precise pronunciation of sounds), clarity (distinct and intelligible wording), projection (properly resonant voice, as opposed to whispering), coherence (the avoidance of stuttering or unnecessary repetitions), and control (the elimination of verbal tics). An analysis of these specific aspects, monitored during the students' podcast presentations, reveals that at least one student in 18 out of the 41 total groups failed to meet these indicators. While these findings are not alarming, they suggest a need for increased pedagogical focus on this area, considering the students are preparing for teaching careers. Regarding pausing, the study examined the duration (short, medium, or long), the

function (breathing, cognitive processing, or transitioning between ideas), and the positioning (preceding or following a key point). For the majority of students, pauses were effectively integrated into the dialogue, predominantly being of short duration and utilized to signal a shift in thought or the direction of the discussion.

With regard to rhythm, the analysis focused on: tempo (fast, moderate, or slow), variability (constant versus varied rhythm), fluency (natural flow versus staccato delivery), and adaptation (rhythm adjusted according to emotion, content, or audience). The observed rhythmic patterns were diverse, ranging from rapid to slow, although a varied rhythm was encountered in most cases. While the students correctly employed communicative pauses and maintained a tempo conducive to message comprehension, further emphasis must be placed on stress and tonality. Stress provides formative insights as it conveys data regarding message clarity, the structuring of ideas, and emotional intensification. The study examined logical stress (emphasizing the main idea), affective stress (conveying emotion), regional accent (local pronunciation particularities), and intentional stress (utilized for persuasion or clarification). Regarding tonality, the investigation considered: pitch (low, medium, high), modulation (natural or forced variations in tone), timbre (warm, metallic, nasal, grave, or bright), and emotional intent (calm, authoritative, playful, or tonic tones). Among male students, high or grave tones were predominant; however, a varied tonality prevailed overall. Essential to oral communication, stress and tonality do not merely transmit how something is said, but also reflect how we think, relate, and construct our communicative identity. The analysis concludes that students require further development in expressivity and persuasion, interpretation and comprehension, as well as linguistic awareness.

Other aspects are equally significant in podcast presentations, contributing to the formative dimension of student learning; these include the announcement of the topic, the introduction of interlocutors, the use of a musical background, and a coherent structure. Although seemingly less critical at first glance, these elements possess formative value for several reasons: (1) announcing the topic at the outset ensures communicative clarity, provides direction, and organizes the discourse; (2) introducing the dialogue partner reflects communicative ethics, builds credibility, and highlights social and interpersonal skills; (3) selecting a musical background (sound design) stimulates expressiveness, creates a pleasant and relaxed atmosphere, and develops media competencies; (4) structural coherence demonstrates information organization and the ability to construct a logical discourse, thereby fostering academic speaking skills. The analysis of the results suggests that while a significant majority of students maintained a coherent presentation structure (80.49 %), a much smaller proportion utilized a musical background (19.51 %). Educators should encourage creativity; our working hypothesis was that incorporating soundscapes can stimulate students' creative expressions (as sound assists students in multimodal thinking, facilitates the expression of emotions and intentions, prompts more creative decision-making, and encourages thinking in terms of audio production). We observed that those who employed a musical background (whether

during specific segments or throughout the entire presentation) exhibited higher levels of expressiveness, relaxation, and motivation.

6. Limitations

Primarily, this study focused on the formative potential of podcasting for students, without addressing the problematic aspects or challenges that necessitate an adaptation of this tool within the instructional-educational process. Although no existing research suggests that podcasts have a detrimental effect on learning, several questions remain for educators and researchers to address (e.g., "How do students manage their time when creating a podcast as an applied assignment?", "Which specific elements require the most attention during the production or presentation of a podcast?", and "Does the use of podcasts as an applied task possess the same formative value across all academic disciplines?"). On one hand, while podcast production is engaging and formative, some students are reluctant to develop the technical skills required for production. This lack of engagement often stems from a deficiency in technical and digital literacy, which can become a supplementary source of stress and evaluation anxiety (particularly when grades are involved or time constraints are stringent). On the other hand, within student groups characterized by low cohesion or insufficient socialization, there is invariably at least one student who encounters difficulties in securing a partner to complete the collaborative task.

Secondly, the descriptive analysis that was conducted is a first step in scientific research and, therefore, additional studies are needed, complementing the approach with an interpretative analysis and, for a more in-depth investigation of the topic, with an experimental analysis.

7. Conclusions

Student podcasting fosters a dynamic and engaging learning experience. In this context, the transformative potential of podcasts for a more open, collaborative, and socially engaged academic environment is observed. We also believe that preparing and presenting a podcast is an activity with complex formative valences: it develops communication, cognitive capacities, collaboration, technical skills, emotional self-regulation. Future studies should explore the pedagogical and cost benefits of podcasting in higher education, compared to other methods.

Our research shows how podcasting can empower learners (help them become more active and independent) and how student-created podcasts can promote student engagement, enhance cognitive learning, and develop teamwork skills. Overall, these results show that involving students in producing and presenting podcast content is a positive, formative learning experience.

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